

DETERMINATION OF GEOMETRICAL PARAMETERS FOR ELECTRICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF A CFRP DURING CURING

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ABSTRACT

The present paper proposes to study the changes in the geometrical parameters of a unidirectional composite material made of T700/M21 prepregs during the cure cycle in the aim to model its electrical behaviour during curing. For this work, an experimental approach has been developed to monitor the changes in the following parameters: volume and surface ratios, percolation parameters and thicknesses taking the rheological transitions into account during an oven cure. Then, micro-structural analyses (in the three orthotropic planes) were carried out to define different empirical laws traducing the changes in these parameters during curing. This enables us to determine the electrical model of resistance $R(\Omega)$ and capacitance $C(F)$ during curing. In this context, we propose to study a percolation model predicting the changes in the electrical resistive behaviour at the ply scale of the present material during curing taking the influence of the micro-structural parameters into account. Obtained results of this model were compared with those measured during curing. Good agreement was obtained between the measured and predicted electrical resistance during curing.

1 INTRODUCTION

The idea of cure monitoring of composite materials is in progress nowadays. For this purpose, various techniques, such as electrical measurements are used during curing in the aim of reducing processing time and improving the properties of the composite structures manufactured. However, the comprehension of the electrical mechanisms of conduction of such material has so far received little attention. In fact, the electrical values are not only affected just by the high anisotropy and design of the composite material but also by the changes in the rheological and geometrical parameters (volume and surface ratios, percolation parameters and thicknesses) during curing. All these parameters must be taken into account to establish electrical models traducing the changes of the electrical anisotropic resistive behavior during curing. The present paper proposes to study the changes in the geometrical and electrical parameters of an oven-cured composite material made of T700/M21 prepregs during the cure cycle. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In section 1, we expose an analytic law allowing determining the changes in the transverse electrical resistance taking the influence of the anisotropic geometrical parameters into account. Then, we present the developed experimental approach to define the geometrical parameters during an oven curing. In section 3, a final analysis is proposed not only to link the results obtained to the different curing steps but also to highlight potential laws that could serve the electrical resistive model during curing. Finally, we summarize our results and draw some conclusions.

1.1 Transverse electrical resistive conduction of UD composite material

The structure of a single CFRP ply is described in Figure 1. It made of carbon fibres with N_T fibres seen in a cross section (\perp to L axis) and N_{th} fibres through the thickness ply tp . embedded in an insulating matrix. The electrical conduction in the transverse direction depends strongly on the volume ratio and the morphology of the fibres in the ply. In fact, the conductivity in the direction transverse to the fibers is not zero (it laying between 10 and 100 S/m). This is due to a percolation network defined by contacts between fibres which are not perfectly aligned and not perfectly covered by the matrix. These contacts resulted mainly from the inhomogeneous distribution and the waving of fibres generated by the lay-up step and the resin contraction during curing. Xia et al [1] and Park et al [2] demonstrated that the length of the fibre segments between contacts in the plane (L. T), δec (Figure 1), was the main parameter of the electrical conductivity in the transverse direction. This latter is linked to the volume ratio of fibres, V_f , but also to the number of contact points defined in the (T. Z) plan (T. Z). N_c .

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the electrical current path in the transverse direction.

As regards the determination of δec , Xia et al [1] showed that the average length of the fibre segments between contacts in the ply could be defined as:

$$\delta ec = L.N/2.N_c \quad (1)$$

Where “2” is a factor introduced because each contact point connects two fibres. L is the length of fibres and N is the total number of fibres in the composite sample.

Here N (the number of fibre linked to the determination of the average values of δec in the whole ply of a width w) and N_{th} (the number of fibre in ply linked to the transverse conduction section of a width w') were deduced from the determination of ply thickness tp and the fibres volume ratio, V_f , as showing the following relation:

$$N_{th} = V_f.tp.w'/v_f \quad \text{and} \quad N = V_f.tp.w/v_f \quad (2)$$

Where v_f is the volume of fibres (mm^3) in the plane (T.Z).

However, N_T was calculated from:

$$N_T = S_f.L.w/s_f \quad (3)$$

Where S_f and s_f are the surface ratio and the surface (mm^2) of fibres in the plane (L.T).

Many models have been developed to estimate the values of δec under mechanical loading. Park et al [2] developed an electro-mechanical model of CFRP composites to predict this parameter under tensile loading. However, Gillet et al.[3] considered that δec could be identified simply by measuring the waving period of fibres using microstructural analyses.

Based on these approaches, Xia et al proposed an analytic model traducing the change in the transverse electrical resistance taking the variations of the percolation parameters into account, using the following relation:

$$R_T = \frac{\rho(\beta\delta_{ce})^2}{N_{th}L} N_T \quad (4)$$

Where ρ is the fibre resistivity and β is the geometry factor (β equals 2 and 2.4 for square and hexagonal fiber distributions. respectively).

The main objective of the present paper is to determine the change in the transverse electrical resistance in the UD T700/M21 plies during curing using the above-mentioned percolation model (1). Here we consider that all the plies present an homogenous geometrical and electrical values during curing. First of all, the experimental protocol leading to the determination of the following geometrical parameters during curing: δ_{ec} , N_T , N_{th} , N , N_c , S_f , V_f and tp taking the different rheological transitions during undergone by the epoxy resin curing into account is presented. Subsequently, the estimated electrical values will be compared to those measured during curing.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL

The materials used for this study were the M21 polymeric matrix system and the T700GC/M21 carbon/polymeric matrix prepreg, both manufactured by Hexcel Composites. The prepreg was supplied as a unidirectional tape with an uncured average ply thickness of 250 μm .

With a given material and given bagging products in an out-of-autoclave curing process, releasing the vacuum at various steps enables laminates to be obtained that have various volume contents (V_f , V_m , V_o) and thicknesses. With a similar aim, Kay et al. simply decided to stop the cure cycle at various times in order to obtain a variety of varying void contents in an out-of-autoclave process [4].

It was decided to rely upon the phase transitions experienced by the M21 resin system during curing to determine the times at which the vacuum would be interrupted while continuing the curing of laminates until the end of the cure cycle. The idea was to "freeze" the microstructure of the plies and the laminates from a geometrical point of view.

Thus, as shown in previous works [5] [6], embedding thin soft copper tapes (used as electrodes) between the plies of a laminate enables the laminate electrical resistance R (Ω) and capacitance C (F) to be simply monitored in real time during a cure cycle. It was demonstrated (as it was also the case in several studies using dielectric measurement systems as in [7] that the changes in laminate R and C could easily be linked to the changes occurring in the composite matrix viscosity during a cure cycle [5].

Figure 2 shows the changes in viscosity (μ), shear moduli (conservative modulus G' and dissipative modulus G'') and loss factor $\tan(\delta)$ recorded during the curing of an unreinforced M21 thermoset/thermoplastic system in a parallel plate rheometer. The temperature conditions (heating ramp at 2°C/min and isothermal dwell at 180°C) were those recommended by the prepreg manufacturer. As shown in Figure 2, up to 10 specific points were spotted on μ , G' , G'' and $\tan(\delta)$ curves. These specific points correspond to minima and are linked to physical state transitions.

In the viscous gel / liquid phase transition, 3 points were chosen: 15 min after the cure started " P_1 " (point chosen before the liquid phase), at 21 min " $\tan(\delta)_{min1}$ " (this corresponds to the first minimum of the loss factor $\tan(\delta)$) and at 35 min, " P_{Tgi} " (the first change in the slope of the viscosity, μ curve).

In the liquid / visco-elastic gel transition, 5 points were chosen: 45min after the cure cycle started " $\tan(\delta)_1$ " (the first inflection point of $\tan(\delta)$), at 67 min " $\tan(\delta)_{min2}$ " (the second minimum point of $\tan(\delta)$), at 73 min PG''_{min} (the minimum of dissipative modulus G''), at 89 min " $\tan(\delta)_2$ " (the second inflection point of $\tan(\delta)$) and at 95 min " PG " (the peak of $\tan(\delta)$ corresponding to the gel point).

Finally, in the visco-elastic/vitreous gel transition, 2 points were selected: 117 min after the start of the cure cycle PG''_3 (the third inflection point of G'') and at 187 min " PF " (the end of cross-linking when α remains steady).

Figure 2: Rheological characteristic points chosen for the study (μ : viscosity; G' : conservative modulus; G'' : dissipative modulus; $\tan(\delta)$: loss factor)

3 RESULTS

3.1 Microstructure of monoply T700/M21

Up to 1250 micrographs were made to highlight the changes in the geometrical parameters in the three orthotropic planes of the T700/M21 laminates. In the current paper only the results concerning the microstructure of a one ply are considered. Before studying the electrical behavior of T700/M21 plies, it is necessary to define the components distribution through the thickness of one ply (250 μm thick) (Figure 3). First of all, it should be noted that each ply is constituted of two $\frac{1}{2}$ plies separated by a resin interface. Thermoplastic nodules and porosities can also be detected. The epoxy resin M21 is a heterogeneous system composed of pure resin, nodules with larger diameter than the one of the fibres and dispersed porosities. This observation is consistent with similar microscopic results of the same material [8]. Thus, in the context of electrical characterization, it is of paramount importance to take into account the fibres distribution (conductive part) and heterogeneous composition of the matrix (insulating part).

Figure 3: Microstructural observations of the thickness of cured one ply T700/M21 in the planes (L. T) (a), (L. Z) (b) and (T. Z) (c)

3.2 Changes in the thicknesses of plies during curing

Figure 4 shows the variations of the average values of thicknesses of plies obtained for planes (T. Z) and (L. Z) during curing taking the rheological transitions of the epoxy resin into account. Due to sampling, small deviations were observed on experimental measurements between the two planes (L. Z) and (T. Z).

Figure 4: Changes in the average values of thicknesses of plies tp in planes (L. Z) and (T. Z) during curing. Measurements made after curing at room temperature.

Power laws could be defined owing to the setting up of the percolation model (1). The measured obtained values were in good agreement with the rheological transitions and highlighted 3 characteristic parts. The first part (from the start to P_{tgi}) was linked to the visco-gel /liquid transition and characterized by a rapid reduction of the thicknesses. The second part (from P_{tgi} to PG) exhibited a slower reduction of the thickness, corresponding to the liquid/visco-elastic gel transition. The last one (from PG to PF) was characterized by a near-stabilization of the thickness linked to the visco-elastic/vitreous gel transition. The first two parts were also governed by the flow mechanisms. Similar results have been reported by Loos and Springer [9].

3.3 Changes in the surface ratio of fibres S_f during curing

An initial campaign of manual microstructural analyses was carried out to obtain S_f in the three orthotropic planes of such ply of laminate during curing. As the time required to do this manually was very long, it was decided to develop an automatic method for the next campaigns. Image J software was used in both the manual and automatic approaches. The manual approach consists of visually detecting thresholds in the intensity spectrum (grey levels) to highlight 3 phases: fibres, matrix and porosities. In the manual approach, we started by defining the fibres (whiter levels) and their contours. Secondly, porosities (darker levels) were defined in the same way. The matrix phase was thus deduced. To automate this, a tri-phasic medium was considered and using an Otsu 3 thresholding approach seemed to be an answer. The fibre surface ratios obtained with this automatic approach “Otsu3” were in good agreement with those found by the manual approach (Table. 1). Nevertheless, in the plane (L. T) there were higher standard deviations. This can be explained by the fact that hand polishing could not insure good repeatability of the polishing depth on the upper surface of the laminate. The surface ratios of plies obtained in planes (L. T) and (L. Z) were different from the volume ratios determined by chemical analyses as in [10].

	S_f (%) (L.T)	S_f (%) (L.Z)	S_f (%) (T.Z)	V_f (%) Global values
<i>Manuel method</i>	55.02±11.08	48.47±1.60	50.22±0.907	—
<i>Automatic method</i>	57.35±5.41	48.84±1.06	51.23±1.11	—
<i>Chemical dissolution</i>	—	—	—	51.75±3.33

Table 1: Comparison between the average surface ratios S_f obtained by manual and automatic approaches for the 3 orthotropic planes of plies (Point PF taken as an example here).

The automatic approach can be considered to be the more reliable as it was less time consuming and always gave the lowest standard deviations. Thus, in the following lines, only automatic measurements will be presented. Figure 5 shows the changes in the average automatic fibre surface ratios in the plies during curing for planes (L. T), (L. Z) and (T. Z) of plies.

Figure 4: Changes in the average automatically determined values of S_f in plies during curing.

As previously, power laws could be defined to describe the evolution of S_f and V_f during curing. It was observed that $S_{f(L,T)}$ represented the highest values (mainly equal to S_f in the prepreg $\sim 56.9\%$) and $S_{f(L,Z)}$ the lowest ones. $S_{f(T,Z)}$ started from the lowest values and tended towards the highest. Here the fibre volume ratio V_f is considered equal to S_f obtained in the (T. Z) plane ($S_{f(T,Z)}=V_f$). As V_f is the major parameter used to define the electrical conduction, the results concerning the volume ratios of resin and porosities are not presented here.

3.4 Changes in the percolation parameters during curing

The 3D network percolation is linked to the percolation distances δ_{ec} in plane (L. T) and to the number of contacts between adjacent fibres N_c (in plane (T. Z)) of ply (figure 1). The determination of the percolation parameters (δ_{ec} ; N_c) during curing of the composite has received little attention. In this section, the average values of δ_{ec} and N_c are determined during curing using microstructural analyses. To determine δ_{ec} , an automatic method was developed to measure N_c on up to 600 micrographs using the “Binary Watershed” method in the aim of saving time. The following figures expose the changes of obtained values of N_c , N_T and N_{th} versus the V_f in the plies during curing:

Figure 5: N (a), N_c (b), N_{th} (c), N_T (d), vs V_f in the plies during curing.

Subsequently, based on equation (1), δ_{ec} was determined from $Ptgi$ to the end of polymerisation PF as shown in the following figure:

Figure 6: Changes in the average values of δ_{ec} in the plies during curing.

Figure 5 shows that N , N_c , N_{th} and N_T increased during curing. However, Figure 6 shows that δ_{ec} drops significantly from $Ptgi$ until PG (fibre contacts are not fixed; thickness reduction and resin flow linked to the sharp decline of the viscosity from $Ptgi$, see Figure 2) and exhibits quasi-linear behaviour thereafter.

3.5 Changes in the transverse electrical resistance during curing

In this last section, we compare the estimated and measured values of the transverse electrical resistance R_T in the plane (L, T) of T700/M21 sample during curing. To ensure the measurements of R_T during curing, we used flexible printed circuits which are called “flex”. These are made of a 50 μm thick polyimide film (good compatibility with the M21 resin) and a 35 μm thick copper/gold-metallized band. Two flex were placed transversally to the fibres in the plan (L,T) to measure the transversal resistance of T700/M21 sample (100mm x 100mm x 2mm) during curing as described in Figure 7. The values of the R_T measured at 30 kHz were extracted for the purpose (Collaboration with LAAS Laboratory).

Figure 6: Insertion of flexes for transversal resistance measurement during curing.

The following figure exposes the changes in the measured and estimated values of R_T during curing from the start of liquefaction step (*Ptgi*) to the end of the polymerization (*PF*):

Figure 7: Comparison between the measured and estimated values of R_T during curing.

From these tendencies, we can deduce that the measured values of R_T tended toward those estimated using the percolation model defined by Xia et al [1] considering a hexagonal distribution of fibres ($\beta = 2.4$) more than toward the square one ($\beta = 2$). This appears coherent to the real distribution of T700

carbon fires of the studied material. A gap is highlighted between the measured and estimated values ($\beta = 2.4$) from *PTgi* until *PG*. From *PG*, the two curves converged significantly. This can be explained by the absence of the contact between the ply and the used electrodes during the liquefaction step (and the flow of the resin). From *PG*, the structure freezes and the electrodes remain in contact with the ply until the end of polymerization.

This study highlights the significant influence of the micro structural parameters on the change in the transverse electrical resistance of composite material during curing. The T700/M21 composite used here as a sensor of its transverse electrical resistance. This enables us to monitor the cure process using the electrical transverse resistance values. In the next work, an inverse model could be defined to control the cure cycle.

Conclusion

This study deals with the investigation of the transverse electrical resistance of a unidirectional carbon-epoxy composite during curing taking the influence of the anisotropic geometrical parameters into account. For this objective, an analytic percolation model was used to predict the variation of the transverse electrical resistance during curing. Automatic and manual microstructural analyses were carried out to highlight the changes in the studied geometrical parameters during curing in the 3 orthotropic planes of plies. Obtained estimated values of R_T were compared with those measured during curing. The first obtained results are satisfactory and highlight the significant influence of the microstructural parameters on the transverse electrical resistive behavior of composite material during curing.

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